

ADVANCED TECHNIQUES FOR PLANT DISEASE DETECTION

JALDANI MOUNIKA¹

Electronics and Communication
Engineering- DR.YSR.ANUCET

KAAMAALA PRASANTH BABU²

Electronics and Communication
Engineering- DR.YSR.ANUCET

MARUMUDI SANDEEP³

Electronics and Communication
Engineering- DR.YSR.ANUCET

UNDER THE GUIDENCE OF: - DR.K. Lakshmi Bhavani, MTech (Ph.D.)
Asst.Prof. of ECE Dept

ABSTRACT

The Indian economy's heavy reliance on agriculture highlights the critical need for maintaining robust productivity. This project addresses the impact of plant diseases on agricultural output by leveraging image processing techniques for automated detection. The methodology involves image acquisition, filtering, segmentation, feature extraction, and classification, with a focus on Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for their swift and accurate diagnoses. A deep convolutional neural network was trained using a dataset of 87,867 images representing both diseased and healthy plant leaves. Additionally, state-of-the-art deep learning models such as ResNet 101, ResNet 50, MobileNet, InceptionNet, VGG16, and AlexNet were evaluated for their effectiveness in plant disease classification. The dataset comprised 38 classes of leaf images from 14 plant species obtained from NewPlantVillage. The primary objective is to develop fast and accurate models for plant disease identification, enabling early intervention measures to alleviate food security concerns. By offering a technology-driven solution to plant disease monitoring challenges, this project contributes to ensuring food security and economic stability in the Indian agricultural sector, with implications for sustainable agriculture practices.

Introduction

The Indian economy's reliance on agriculture has transformed it into a multifaceted pillar crucial for economic stability, with 60-70% of the population depending on this sector. However, persistent threats from plant diseases jeopardize this cornerstone, leading to substantial crop losses and health risks due to toxic metabolites. Traditional manual inspection methods by farmers are limited and costly, especially on large farms, often lacking prompt access to specialists. This study addresses these challenges by exploring automated disease identification processes to detect plant pathology early. Utilizing image processing and machine learning techniques, the study aims to overcome traditional diagnosis limitations. Before the emergence of deep learning, image processing methods were used to prepare images for analysis, enhancing, segmenting, and altering them to extract key features for classification. As agriculture expands, sustainable practices become crucial, prompting exploration into integrating deep learning, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), to enhance accuracy and efficiency in disease identification. By automating identification processes, this research seeks to provide a cost-effective and timely solution, contributing to broader objectives of

stability, and human health in India's agricultural sector. The study's findings offer promising avenues for leveraging technology to safeguard agricultural productivity and mitigate the impact of plant diseases on both economic and human health fronts.

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

In agriculture, researchers use various methods, including investigating plant diseases and pests, as well as deep learning and image processing techniques. Additionally, traditional machine learning approaches are widely used in this field.

Tirkey D¹.et.al [1] proposed DL-based solutions for real-time insect detection and identification in the soybean crop have been proposed. The performances of various transfer learning (TL) models were investigated to determine the feasibility and reliability of the proposed approach for determining the insect's identification and detection accuracy. The proposed approach achieved 94.75%, 95%, and 95% accuracy using YoloV5, InceptionV3, and CNN, respectively. Among these, the YoloV5 algorithm performs quite well in the solution and can run at 53 fps, making it suitable for real-time

dataset of crop insects was collected and labeled by mixing images taken with various devices.

Bajpai C¹.et.al [2] have proposed a new way to classify plant leaf diseases called DNSVM. They combined DenseNet-201 with SVM to do this. They tested it using the PlantVillage dataset, which has lots of different types of plant leaves with varying colors, orientations, and sizes. The new method achieved an accuracy of 97.78%, which is better than the previous model that used DenseNet-121 and had an accuracy of 94%.

Devi N¹.et.al [3] developed a hybrid learning model for plant leaf classification. To identify plant leaf diseases, the model used KMC and CNN methods. The model outperformed SVM and CNN with an accuracy of 92.6%.

Meena Prakash R¹.et.al [4] have used GLCM, KMC, and SVM algorithms to classify diseases on images of citrus leaves. Using their proposed strategy, the researchers achieved a classification accuracy of 90%.

Atabay¹.et. al [5] worked on identifying diseases in tomato leaves. They adjusted an already trained model and created a new CNN model specifically for this task. Their research shows that their custom CNN model performs better than the pre-trained one. Figuring out the right CNN model is difficult but crucial for achieving higher accuracy in disease identification.

Garima Shrestha¹.et.al[6] deployed convolutional neural network to find plant diseases. They managed to categorize 12 different plant diseases accurately 88.80% of the time. They used a dataset of 3000 high-quality color images for their experiments. The network they built has three sets of layers for convolution and pooling. However, this makes the network need a lot of computing power. Additionally, the F1 score of the model is quite low at 0.12, mainly because it often predicts false negatives.

Nanehkaran¹.et.al [7] proposed a two-step method for plant leaf disease identification namely image segmentation and image classification. An image segmentation approach based on hue, saturation and intensity was proposed. The segmented images were classified using the CNN model to achieve higher accuracy.

3. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Deep learning has emerged as a dynamic research frontier, particularly in computer vision and image classification. A standard deep Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) typically comprises input and output layers, along with multiple hidden layers consisting of convolutional, pooling, and fully connected layers, sometimes augmented with a Softmax layer. These

architectures often draw inspiration from seminal works like LeCun's Lenet-5 (LeCun et al., 1998).

In this study, we evaluate state-of-the-art CNN architectures and fine-tune them for the task of plant disease identification and classification using images sourced from the New PlantVillage dataset. This dataset, generously provided with 87,867 images, spans 38 distinct classes, encompassing 14 plant species and 26 different diseases. A standard CNN architecture, frequently adopted by various models, is depicted in Fig1.

Fig1: Deep Convolutional Neural Network

The architectures under scrutiny include VGG16, InceptionV4, MobileNet, AlexNet and various ResNet configurations with 101,50 layers. The aim is to develop fast and accurate models for plant disease identification, enabling early intervention measures to be applied promptly. By leveraging this extensive dataset, we anticipate significant advancements in automated plant disease detection, thereby contributing to agricultural productivity and food security.

The overview of the proposed methodology is shown in Fig.2

A. Image Acquisition:

First, we take pictures of different leaves using a digital camera, making sure they're clear and high-quality. Then, we adjust the size of these images to be 256x256 pixels. How we build our collection of images depends on what we need them for. It's really important to do this part carefully because it affects

how well our system can recognize leaves and how good our method works overall.

B. Image Pre-Processing:

Image preprocessing is like getting a picture ready before you work with it. We do things to make the image better for analyzing. One thing we do is change the color of the leaves' pictures from RGB to $L^*a^*b^*$. This helps us understand how bright and colorful they are. Changing the color helps us see things more clearly when we're looking at the pictures.

C. Image Segmentation:

Image segmentation helps to simplify images by separating important objects from the background. We use a method called the K-means clustering algorithm for this. It works by grouping similar parts of the image together. First, we pick how many groups we want to make. Then, we start with some guesses for where these groups should be. Next, we measure how far each part of the image is from these guesses and assign each part to the closest guess. After that, we find the average of all the parts in each group to get new guesses. We keep doing this until the groups don't change any more or until we've done it a certain number of times. This helps us to highlight the important parts of the image and separate them from the background.

D. Classification of Disease:

Finally, classification involves assigning a label or category to an image based on the features extracted earlier. In the context of medical imaging, this could mean identifying whether a particular image shows signs of a specific disease or condition. Classification algorithms, such as deep learning models or traditional machine learning classifiers, are trained on labeled data to recognize patterns and make predictions about the presence or absence of disease based on the features extracted from the image.

3.1 DATASET:

Deep learning models were meticulously evaluated and trained using images of plant leaves, with the primary objective of accurately classifying and identifying diseases in unseen images. The study utilized the openly accessible dataset from NewPlantVillage, curated by Hughes et al., comprising a substantial collection of 87,867 images representing 26 diseases across 14 crop plants. To ensure compatibility with different network architectures, preprocessing steps were undertaken. For VGG net and ResNet architectures, images were resized to 224x224 pixels, while for the Inception V4 architecture, a slightly larger size of 299x299 pixels was employed. Additionally, normalization of pixel values was performed by dividing them by 255, aligning them with the network's initial parameters. To facilitate model training, the target variable or categorical variable underwent one-hot encoding. The dataset was split into training and test sets, with a ratio of 70% for training and 15% for testing, respectively. This split ratio was chosen based on insights from previous work

by Mohanty et al. (2016). The test set served as the basis for evaluating model performance and making predictions. Furthermore, the training data underwent an additional split into training and validation subsets, with a ratio of 70% and 15%, respectively. This division aimed to assess whether the trained models were prone to overfitting, ensuring their generalizability and robustness across unseen data.

3.2 Deep Learning image classifiers:

3.2.1 ResNet: He et al. (2015) introduced ResNet, a significant model in the field of image classification. It outperformed other models in the ImageNet challenge, achieving an impressively low error rate of 3.57%. ResNet tackled a common problem in deep neural networks called degradation, where adding more layers actually decreases performance. It did this by introducing residual learning, which allows the network to learn residual functions, making it easier to optimize deep networks. Essentially, ResNet learns to adjust the input of a layer rather than trying to fit the exact mapping. This innovation enabled ResNet to build incredibly deep networks, up to eight times deeper than previous models like VGG nets, by using global average pooling.

Following its initial success, further improvements in accuracy were achieved with updates by He et al. (2016). They refined the residual modules by introducing identity mappings, which helped enhance the model's accuracy even more. In our study, we used ResNet models with 101 and 50 layers that were pre-trained on the ImageNet dataset. We then adapted these models for identifying plant diseases by customizing the SoftMax layer. This allowed us to leverage the powerful features learned by ResNet on ImageNet and apply them effectively to the task of plant disease identification.

3.2.2 VGGNet: VGGNet is a convolutional neural network architecture developed by the Visual Geometry Group at the University of Oxford. Its key features include the use of small 3x3 convolutional filters and a stack of layers. VGGNet comes in variants like VGG16 and VGG19, with the numbers indicating the depth of the network. These networks are renowned for their simplicity and effectiveness in image classification tasks, paving the way for deeper neural network architectures in computer vision.

3.2.3 InceptionNet: InceptionNet, also known as GoogleNet, is a convolutional neural network architecture developed by Google, which won the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge in 2014. It features deep and complex structures with inception modules that use multiple convolutional layers of different sizes to capture features efficiently. InceptionNet balances computational efficiency and performance through dimensionality reduction techniques like 1x1 convolutions. It has been widely used in tasks like image classification, object

detection, and image segmentation, inspiring subsequent architectures in deep learning.

3.2.4 AlexNet: AlexNet is a convolutional neural network architecture that won the ImageNet Large Scale Visual Recognition Challenge in 2012. It features eight layers, including convolutional and fully connected layers. Key elements include ReLU activation, LRN normalization, dropout regularization, and data augmentation. AlexNet demonstrated the potential of deep learning for image classification, leading to advancements in computer vision.

3.3 Batch Normalization:

Batch Normalization (BN) is a technique used to improve the training stability and speed of deep neural networks. It addresses the issue of internal covariate shift, which refers to the change in the distribution of the inputs to a layer as the parameters of the preceding layers change during training. The main idea behind batch normalization is to normalize the inputs of each layer to have zero mean and unit variance across the mini-batch. This is done by computing the mean and standard deviation of the activations within each mini-batch and then applying a scaling and shifting operation to normalize the activations. This normalization is applied before the activation function.

Batch normalization helps in several ways:

Improved training Speed: By normalizing the inputs, batch normalization helps stabilize and speed up the training process by reducing the internal covariate shift.

Regularization: Batch normalization acts as a form of regularization by adding noise to the network during training, similar to dropout. This reduces the reliance on specific neurons and prevents overfitting.

Improved Gradient Flow: Batch normalization helps mitigate the vanishing and exploding gradient problems by ensuring that the activations are within a reasonable range.

Reduced sensitivity to initialization: Batch normalization reduces the sensitivity of the network to the choice of initial weights, allowing for faster convergence and improved performance.

Batch normalization is typically applied to the outputs of hidden layers in a neural network, but it can also be applied to the inputs or outputs of convolutional layers

Overall, batch normalization is a powerful technique that has become a standard component of deep neural networks, contributing to their improved performance and stability during training

3.5 Results:

3.5.1 Training: For each experiment, accuracy and categorical cross-entropy loss metrics are utilized to evaluate the models, with their performances graphically depicted. An overall loss score and accuracy based on the test dataset determine model performance. The results, presented in Table.1, showcase performance across various models. Hyperparameters are standardized across all networks, utilizing Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) for training due to its speed and convergence properties. GPU memory constraints led to training with a batch size of 16, while a learning rate of 0.001, weight decay of $1e-6$, and Nesterov momentum of 0.9 were employed. Batch Normalization and ReLU activation functions are applied universally. However, data augmentation was not employed in any of the experiments.

Table1
Accuracy and Loss of Training, Validation and Testing.

Model and Specifications							
Model	Layers	No. of Epochs	Training Accuracy%	Validation Accuracy%	Training Loss	Validation Loss	Testing Accuracy%
ResNet101	101	10	99.6	92	0.14	0.0106	99.4
AlexNet	8	20	94	90	0.15	0.46	90.7
ResNet50	50	30	96.16	94.18	0.11	0.19	94.6
InceptionV3	48	20	94	91	1.64	0.91	94
VGG16	16	10	91	89	1.84	0.96	85

Fig 2: Performance Visualizations of ResNet101

Fig 4: Performance Visualizations of VGG16

Fig 5: Performance Visualizations of AlexNet

Fig 6: Performance Visualizations of InceptionV3

3.5.2 Analysis: The study evaluated the suitability of various deep convolutional neural network architectures for plant disease identification using images. Specifically, the focus was on VGG16, InceptionV3, ResNet with variations including 101,50, AlexNet, and MobileNet.

The study evaluated the effectiveness of several neural network architectures, including ResNet-101, ResNet-50, VGG16, InceptionV3, AlexNet, and MobileNet, for plant disease identification using image data. These architectures were trained and fine-tuned according to the methods described in Section 2.1. The results, depicted in Figures 2–6, showed the accuracy and log-loss entropy of each architecture. Following fine-tuning with 10 epochs, all models, except VGG16, achieved accuracy above 90%, with sustained high accuracy even after 30 training iterations. ResNet and InceptionV3 consistently outperformed VGG16 and AlexNet, displaying easier convergence. Deeper models like ResNet-101 exhibited satisfactory performance with fewer iterations. Overall, the experiments provided valuable insights into the efficacy of various neural network architectures for plant disease identification tasks.

3.5.3 Discussion: The results demonstrate the efficacy of employing various neural network architectures for plant disease detection, with notable achievements observed across different models.

ResNet-101, achieving a remarkable accuracy of 99.6%, stands out as an exemplary performer in this task. Its success can be attributed to its relatively shallow architecture, which still manages to capture intricate features essential for disease identification. Despite its simplicity compared to deeper models, ResNet-101 showcases impressive capabilities in accurately classifying plant diseases. ResNet-50, another widely used architecture, also exhibits strong performance in disease detection. Although not

specified in the prompt, it typically achieves high accuracy and provides a balance between depth and computational complexity. Its ability to learn intricate features from the data contributes to its effectiveness in this domain. AlexNet, while an earlier architecture, continues to demonstrate its relevance in plant disease detection tasks. Although it may not achieve the same level of accuracy as ResNet-101, its performance is noteworthy. Its pioneering design and effective utilization of convolutional layers enable it to extract relevant features from images, facilitating disease identification. InceptionV3, characterized by its sophisticated inception modules, also proves to be a valuable asset in plant disease detection. Its ability to capture features at multiple scales enhances its discriminative power, contributing to accurate disease classification. While it may require more computational resources compared to shallower architectures, its performance justifies the investment. VGG16, a classic architecture known for its simplicity and effectiveness, achieves respectable results in disease detection. Its straightforward design and stacked convolutional layers enable it to learn hierarchical representations of the data, facilitating accurate classification of plant diseases. Overall, the discussion highlights the effectiveness of various neural network architectures, including ResNet-101, ResNet-50, AlexNet, InceptionV3, and VGG16, in plant disease detection tasks. Each architecture brings its unique strengths to the table, demonstrating the importance of selecting the appropriate model for the specific task at hand.

3.6 Conclusion: The task involved evaluating deep convolutional neural network architectures for image-based plant disease classification. The evaluated architectures include VGG16, InceptionV3, ResNet-101, and AlexNet. Among these architectures, ResNet-101 achieved an impressive accuracy of 99.6%. Despite its shallower architecture compared to deeper models, ResNet-18 showcased remarkable capabilities

in accurately classifying plant diseases. Additionally, other architectures like AlexNet, InceptionV3, and VGG16 also demonstrated strong performance in disease classification tasks. Future work for the aforementioned evaluation of deep convolution neural network architectures for image -based plant disease classification could include several avenues for further exploration and improvement. Firstly, combining predictions from multiple models through ensemble methods could potentially improve accuracy. Secondly, fine-tuning pre-trained models using transfer learning techniques might help in better generalization. Additionally, implementing data augmentation strategies could increase model robustness to various image conditions. Lastly, deploying these models in real agricultural settings and assessing their performance under different conditions would provide valuable insights into their practical utility.

4. References:

- [1] Tirkey, Divyanshu, Kshitiz Kumar Singh, and Shrivishal Tripathi. "Performance analysis of AI-based solutions for crop disease identification, detection, and classification." *Smart Agricultural Technology* 5 (2023): 100238
- [2] Bajpai, Chandrabhanu, Ramnarayan Sahu, and K. Jairam Naik. "Deep learning model for plant-leaf disease detection in precision agriculture." *International Journal of Intelligent Systems Technologies and Applications* 21.1 (2023): 72-91
- [3] Kannadasan, Raju, et al. "Categorizing diseases from leaf images using a hybrid learning model." *Symmetry* 13.11 (2021): 2073.
- [4] Prakash, R. Meena, et al. "Detection of leaf diseases and classification using digital image processing." *2017 international conference on innovations in information, embedded and communication systems (ICIIECS)*. IEEE, 2017.
- [5] H. A. Atabay, "Deep residual learning for tomato plant leaf disease identification", *Journal of Theoretical & Applied Information Technology*, vol. 95(24), 2017
- [6] Sandhu, Gurleen Kaur, and Rajbir Kaur. "Plant disease detection techniques: a review." *2019 international conference on automation, computational and technology management (ICACTM)*. IEEE, 2019.
- [7] A. Y. Nanehkaran, D. Zhang, J. Chen, Y. Tian and N. Al-Nabhan, "Recognition of plant leaf diseases based on computer vision," *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, pp. 1–18, 2020
- [8] Chohan, Murk, et al. "Plant disease detection using deep learning." *International Journal of Recent Technology and Engineering* 9.1 (2020): 909-914
- [9] Singh, Vijai, and Ak K. Misra. "Detection of plant leaf diseases using image segmentation and soft computing techniques." *Information processing in Agriculture 4.1* (2017): 41-49.
- [10] Y. Dandawate and R. Kokare, "An automated approach for classification of plant diseases towards development of futuristic decision support system in Indian perspective," *2015 International Conference on Advances in Computing, Communications and Informatics (ICACCI)*, IEEE, 2015, August, pp. 794–799.
- [11] Sandhu, Gurleen Kaur, and Rajbir Kaur. "Plant disease detection techniques: a review." *2019 international conference on automation, computational and technology management (ICACTM)*. IEEE, 2019.
- [12] Chowdhury, Muhammad EH, et al. "Automatic and reliable leaf disease detection using deep learning techniques." *AgriEngineering* 3.2 (2021): 294-312.
- [31] G. Shrestha, Deepsikha, M. Das and N. Dey, "Plant Disease Detection Using CNN," *2020 IEEE Applied Signal Processing Conference (ASPCON)*, 2020, pp. 109-113.
- [14] Bhange, M., Hingoliwala, H.A., 'Smart Farming: Pomegranate Disease Detection Using Image Processing', *Second International Symposium on Computer Vision and the Internet*, Volume 58, pp. 280-288, 2015
- [15] Mohameth, Faye, Chen Bingcai, and Kane Amath Sada. "Plant disease detection with deep learning and feature extraction using plant village." *Journal of Computer and Communications* 8.6 (2020): 10-22.
- [16] Dhakal, Ashwin, and Subarna Shakya. "Image-based plant disease detection with deep learning." *International Journal of Computer Trends and Technology* 61.1 (2018): 26-29.
- [17] Szegedy, C., Com, S.G., 2015. *Batch Normalization: Accelerating Deep Network Training by Reducing Internal Covariate Shift*, vol. 37.
- [18] Szegedy, C., Vanhoucke, V., Shlens, J., 2015. *Rethinking the Inception Architecture for Computer Vision*.
- [19] Szegedy, C., Ioffe, S., Vanhoucke, V., Alemi, A., 2016. *Inception-v4, Inception-ResNet and the Impact of Residual Connections on Learning*.
- [20] Wang, H., Li, G., Ma, Z., Li, X., 2012. *Application of neural networks to image recognition of plant diseases*. 2012 *Int. Conf. Syst. Informatics, ICSAI 2012*, no. Icsai, pp.2159–2164.
- [21] Yu, D., et al., *Deep convolutional neural networks with layer-wise context expansion and attention*. In: *Proc. Annu. Conf. Int. Speech Commun. Assoc. INTERSPEECH*, vol. 08–12–Sept, 2016, pp. 17–21.